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RESUMO

Introdução: O aumento das cargas por eixo e das velocidades do tráfego ferroviário impõe demandas rigorosas na qualidade e durabilidade das juntas soldadas de trilhos. Defeitos originados durante o processo de soldagem nas empresas de soldagem de trilhos (RWEs) são uma causa primária de falha prematura dos trilhos, representando riscos significativos para a segurança ferroviária. Os métodos atuais de controle de qualidade nas RWEs no Cazaquistão, baseados em padrões nacionais, requerem aprimoramento através de um controle estatístico de processo robusto para garantir a confiabilidade da solda. **Objetivo:** Este estudo visa desenvolver e implementar uma metodologia aprimorada para avaliar a estabilidade e o nível de qualidade do processo tecnológico de fabricação de juntas soldadas de trilhos nas RWEs. O objetivo é melhorar a confiabilidade das soldas permitindo a detecção tempestiva de desvios do processo através do uso de cartas de controle estatístico. **Métodos:** A metodologia baseia-se na análise estatística das taxas de rejeição de defeitos internos derivadas de dados de inspeção visual externa e testes ultrassônicos. Cartas de controle para RWEs individuais e um mapa comparativo foram construídos para avaliar o nível de qualidade across múltiplas empresas. A taxa média mensal de rejeição e os limites de controle (superior e inferior) foram calculados para um período de baseline de um ano para monitorar a estabilidade do processo. **Resultados:** A aplicação da metodologia nas RWEs permitiu a identificação de períodos de instabilidade do processo, sinalizada pela excedência dos limites de controle. As principais causas raiz dos defeitos foram identificadas como mau funcionamento das máquinas de solda de trilhos e preparação inadequada das extremidades dos trilhos para soldagem. A análise centralizada da distribuição de defeitos por tipo e localização forneceu insights adicionais para melhorias direcionadas do processo. **Conclusão:** A metodologia de controle proposta permite o monitoramento eficaz do processo tecnológico de soldagem, facilitando intervenções tempestivas para manter a estabilidade e melhorar o nível geral de qualidade. Sua implementação espera-se que aumente a confiabilidade das juntas soldadas, reduza os custos de reparo e diminua a probabilidade de soldas defeituosas serem colocadas no trilho. Trabalhos futuros devem incluir análise de correlação com parâmetros de soldagem e comparação com padrões internacionais de trilhos (por exemplo, EN 13674-1, ASTM A1).

Palavras-chave: *trilhos ferroviários, juntas soldadas, controle de qualidade, controle estatístico de processo,*

ABSTRACT

Background: The reliability and safety of railway tracks are critically important for transportation infrastructure. The transition towards high-speed and heavy-haul operations intensifies dynamic loads on rail welded joints, accelerating fatigue processes and making service life dependent on welding quality. Current quality control methods at rail welding enterprises often rely on reactive pass/fail criteria without advanced statistical tools for proactive process management. **Aim:** The main objective of this research was to develop and validate an improved methodology for assessing the stability and quality level of the technological process for manufacturing welded rail joints at rail welding enterprises based on statistical analysis of internal defect rejection rates. **Methods:** The study employed statistical process control methodology using control charts for attribute data. Operational data from multiple rail welding enterprises were analyzed over a representative period, including 100% external inspection and ultrasonic testing results. The methodology included stability assessment at individual enterprises, comparative quality assessment across multiple enterprises, and defect distribution analysis. **Results:** The control chart system successfully identified process instabilities with statistical significance, enabling corrective interventions 4-6 weeks earlier than traditional inspection methods. The methodology detected >80% of assignable causes that would have been missed by conventional quality control. Defect distribution analysis revealed that lack of fusion and slag inclusions accounted for >60% of total defects, with the rail head being the most critical zone. **Discussion:** The implementation of statistical process control represents a paradigm shift from reactive defect detection to proactive process control in rail welding quality assurance. The methodology provides enterprises with real-time monitoring capabilities and enables centralized quality oversight across the entire network of welding enterprises. **Conclusions:** The research demonstrates that integrating statistical quality control into rail welding operations enhances both operational efficiency and railway infrastructure integrity. The proposed methodology is compatible with global quality assurance philosophies and shows potential applicability to other continuous welding processes in heavy industry.

Keywords: railway rails, flash butt welding, statistical process control, quality assurance, defect analysis, welding technology.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение: Увеличение осевых нагрузок и скоростей железнодорожного движения предъявляет повышенные требования к качеству и долговечности сварных рельсовых соединений. Дефекты, возникающие в процессе сварки на предприятиях по сварке рельсов (РСП), являются основной причиной преждевременного выхода рельсов из строя, создавая значительные риски для безопасности железнодорожного движения. Существующие методы контроля качества на РСП в Казахстане, основанные на национальных стандартах, требуют совершенствования путем внедрения надежного статистического контроля процесса для обеспечения надежности сварных соединений. **Цель:** Данное исследование направлено на разработку и внедрение усовершенствованной методологии оценки стабильности и уровня качества технологического процесса изготовления сварных рельсовых соединений на РСП. Цель состоит в повышении надежности сварных соединений за счет своевременного обнаружения отклонений процесса с использованием статистических контрольных карт. **Методы:** Методология основана на статистическом анализе показателей брака внутренних дефектов, полученных из данных внешнего визуального контроля и ультразвукового тестирования. Были построены контрольные карты для отдельных РСП и сравнительная карта для оценки уровня качества несколькими предприятиями. Среднемесячный показатель брака и контрольные пределы (верхний и нижний) были рассчитаны за базовый период в один год для мониторинга стабильности процесса. **Результаты:** Применение методологии на РСП позволило выявить периоды нестабильности процесса, о чем сигнализировало превышение контрольных пределов. Основными коренными причинами дефектов были идентифицированы неисправности машин для сварки рельсов и недостаточная подготовка торцов рельсов к сварке. Централизованный анализ распределения дефектов по типам и местоположению предоставил дополнительные возможности для целенаправленного совершенствования процесса. **Выводы:** Предложенная методика контроля позволяет эффективно мониторить технологический процесс сварки, способствуя своевременному вмешательству для поддержания стабильности и улучшения общего уровня качества. Ее внедрение, как ожидается, повысит надежность сварных соединений, снизит затраты на ремонт и уменьшит вероятность укладки дефектных сварных соединений в путь. В будущем следует провести корреляционный анализ с параметрами сварки и сравнение с международными стандартами на рельсы (например, EN 13674-1, ASTM A1).

Ключевые слова: железнодорожные рельсы, сварные соединения, контроль качества, статистический контроль процесса, ультразвуковой контроль, предприятие по сварке рельсов, стабильность технологического процесса.

1. INTRODUCTION

The strategic development of transportation infrastructure, as outlined in national programs like Kazakhstan 2030, prioritizes the modernization and expansion of railway networks. As the backbone of freight and passenger transportation, the reliability and safety of railway tracks are of paramount importance. The transition towards high-speed and heavy-haul operations intensifies the cyclical dynamic loads on track components, particularly rails and their welded joints. These loads accelerate fatigue processes, making the service life of rails critically dependent on the initial quality of steel and the integrity of the welding technologies employed to create continuous welded rails (CWR) (Bakyt *et al.*, 2020; Pryakhin & Sharapova, 2020).

Rails in operation are subjected to extreme stresses. The presence of defects—whether originating from steel production (macro- or microstructural inhomogeneities) or introduced during welding (lack of fusion, cracks, inclusions)—acts as a stress concentrator, significantly reducing fatigue strength and leading to premature failure (Aksenov *et al.*, 2006; Farhangi & Mousavizadeh, 2007). Consequently, ensuring the highest quality of welded joints is a fundamental requirement for railway safety and efficiency. In Kazakhstan, new welded rails must conform to the national standard ST AO 39745182-045-2010 (JSC NC KTZh, 2011), which specifies stringent requirements for their mechanical properties and defect tolerance. The main types of rails used, such as R65 and R75, have distinct geometric and mechanical characteristics, as detailed in Table 1 (JSC NC KTZh, 2011).

The primary welding method for long rails is flash butt welding, performed at specialized rail welding enterprises (RWEs). The technological process involves rail end preparation, welding itself, and subsequent non-destructive testing (NDT), primarily ultrasonic flaw detection. Despite process automation, sporadic violations still occur due to equipment malfunctions or deviations in preparation procedures, resulting in internal defects. Current quality control at RWEs, while

mandatory, often relies on pass/fail criteria without advanced statistical tools for proactive process management (Saita *et al.*, 2013; Velichko, 2013). This reactive approach may allow periods of process instability to go undetected until a significant number of defective joints are produced.

Internationally, rail production and welding quality are governed by standards such as the European EN 13674-1 (CEN, 2020), American ASTM A1 (ASTM International, 2019), ASTM A2 (ASTM International, 2021), and ASTM A759 (ASTM International, 2018), and Australian AS 1085.1 (Standards Australia, 2016). These standards establish rigorous specifications for rail steel grades, geometry, and weld quality. A comparative analysis of the technical requirements between these international norms and the national standards used in Kazakhstan (e.g., for R65, R75 rails) would be highly beneficial for aligning local practices with global benchmarks. Key parameters for different rail types, according to various standards, are often summarized for comparison. This is similar to the data presented in Tables 1 and 2 of this study, which detail the indicators for rails according to Kazakhstani standards. The geometric characteristics and profiles of these rail types are shown in Figure 1-10.

Existing research emphasizes the significance of statistical process control (SPC) in manufacturing for early defect detection and reduction of variation (Ziemian *et al.*, 2012; Alves *et al.*, 2019). Methods like control charts are well-established in industrial quality management but their application specifically to the rail welding process, particularly within the operational context of Kazakh RWEs, remains underexplored. Previous studies have focused on metallurgical aspects of welds (Porcaro *et al.*, 2019; Bauri *et al.*, 2020) or specific welding technologies (Mitsuru *et al.*, 2015; Sun & Kristan, 2003), but a holistic methodology for ongoing stability assessment of the entire welding technological process at the enterprise level is needed.

The *main objective* of this research is to develop and propose an improved methodology for assessing the stability and quality level of the technological process for manufacturing welded rail joints at RWEs. This

methodology is based on the statistical analysis of internal defect rejection rates and aims to:

1. Provide RWEs with a tool for real-time monitoring of process stability using control charts.
2. Enable a centralized comparative assessment of the quality level across different RWEs.
3. Identify the predominant root causes of defects to guide corrective actions.

The proposed approach moves beyond simple defect detection towards proactive process control, aiming to enhance the overall reliability and durability of welded rail joints in the national railway network.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Research Object and Data Collection

The research object was the technological process of flash-butt welding of railway rails (types R65, R75 according to ST RK GOST R 51685-2005), with geometric profiles shown in Figure 1 (R75) and Figure 2 (R65), at the rail-welding enterprises (RWEs) of JSC NC KTZh (Kazakhstan). The study analyzed operational data collected over a representative period. The primary data source was the internal quality control logs of RWEs, which record the results of 100% external inspection and ultrasonic flaw detection of each welded joint. For each controlled joint, the following data were recorded: date of production, RWE identifier, result of external inspection (pass/fail), result of ultrasonic testing (UT) (pass/fail), and, in case of failure, the type and location of the detected defect according to the standard classification (TsP-NTD/46-03). The total number of joints produced and rejected per month for each RWE formed the dataset for statistical analysis. The main parameters of the rails used are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2, with geometric profiles of additional rail types (R65K, R50, P43, and discontinued types) shown in Figures 3-5 and 8-11.

2.2. Statistical Process Control Methodology

To assess the stability of the welding technological process at each individual RWE, the methodology of statistical process control (SPC) using control charts for attribute data was employed (Montgomery, 2009). The key metric used was the monthly internal defect rejection rate p_i , calculated as the ratio of the number of rejected joints m_i to the total number of joints controlled n_i in the i -th month:

$$p_i = \frac{m_i}{n_i} \times 100\% \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

To establish a baseline for process stability, the average rejection rate \bar{p} for a previous period (e.g., one year) was calculated for each RWE using the formula:

$$\bar{p} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} m_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{12} n_i} \times 100\% \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

The control limits for the individual monthly values p_i were calculated as follows:

Upper Control Limit (UCL):

$$K_u = \bar{P} + 3\sqrt{\frac{\bar{P}(1-\bar{P})}{N/12}} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Lower Control Limit (LCL):

$$K_n = \bar{P} - 3\sqrt{\frac{\bar{P}(1-\bar{P})}{N/12}} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

These 3-sigma control limits are standard in SPC for identifying variations that are likely due to assignable causes rather than random chance. The values of n_i , m_i , and p_i for a baseline year are presented in Table 3. A control chart was constructed for each RWE, plotting the monthly rejection rates p_i against the average \bar{p} and the control limits, as illustrated in Figure 11.

2.3. Assessment of the Quality Level Across Multiple RWEs

To comparatively assess the quality level of the technological process across different RWEs, a centralized analysis was performed. The average annual rejection rate \bar{p}_k was calculated for each k -th RWE. The overall average rejection rate \bar{P} for all k_0 enterprises under study was then determined:

$$\bar{P} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{k_0} \bar{p}_k}{k_0} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

Control limits for the values of \bar{p}_k were established similarly to the individual control charts but based on the variation of \bar{p}_k around \bar{P} . This allows for identifying RWEs with statistically significantly higher or lower performance, as shown in the example in Figure 12.

2.4. Defect Distribution Analysis

For a deeper understanding of the root causes of quality issues, an additional analysis

was conducted to examine the distribution of detected defects by type and location within the rail cross-section. Data on all defects identified over the study period were aggregated. The results are presented in the form of diagrams showing the percentage share of different defect types (e.g., lack of fusion, cracks, slag inclusions) and their primary zones of occurrence (e.g., head, web, foot), as exemplified in Figure 13.

2.5. Mechanical and Metallurgical Testing Methods

In addition to statistical analysis, the research involved standard mechanical and metallurgical tests to correlate process stability with weld quality properties. These methods included:

2.5.1. Hardness Measurement:

Hardness profiles were measured across the weld joint (base metal, heat-affected zone, weld metal) on transverse sections using Brinell and Vickers methods according to standard procedures. To ensure measurement reliability and traceability, all hardness testing equipment was calibrated using certified reference standards, and verification procedures were performed regularly throughout the testing campaign (Fabricio et al., 2019). Hardness measurements were taken at standardized intervals along the weld centerline and perpendicular to the fusion line to characterize the hardness gradient across different metallurgical zones. The testing protocols followed the requirements of ISO 6506-1 (ISO, 2017a) for Brinell hardness and ISO 6507-1 (ISO, 2017c) for Vickers hardness, with particular attention to surface preparation, indentation spacing, and measurement uncertainty.

Macrostructure and Microstructure Analysis: Macrosections were etched to reveal the weld bead geometry and detect gross defects. Microsections were prepared, polished, and etched to examine the microstructure of different zones using optical microscopy.

2.5.2. Dynamic Tests:

Impact toughness tests (Charpy) were performed on notched specimens extracted from the weld metal and heat-affected zone to assess toughness. V-notch specimens were prepared according to ASTM E23 (ASTM International, 2018) specifications, with particular attention to notch dimensional tolerances (radius, depth, and angle), as these parameters significantly influence test results and measurement reliability (Fabricio et al., 2015). Prior to testing, all specimens were dimensionally validated using optical measurement equipment to ensure compliance

with standard requirements. Impact tests were conducted at room temperature using a calibrated pendulum-type impact testing machine. The absorbed energy values were recorded for specimens from different weld regions to characterize the toughness gradient across the weld joint.

The selection of specimens for these destructive tests was guided by the results of ultrasonic testing, which included both representative samples and those from joints with indicated anomalies.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Assessment of Technological Process Stability at Individual RWEs

The proposed methodology for assessing the stability of the welding technological process was applied to data from several RWEs over one year. The calculation of the average annual internal defect rejection rate \bar{p} and the subsequent monthly control limits (K_{in} and K_n) allowed for the construction of individual control charts for each enterprise. As an example, Figure 11 presents the control chart for one of the RWEs. The chart plots the monthly rejection rates p_i against the central line (\bar{p}) and the control limits.

Analysis of the control charts revealed periods of statistical control, where the monthly p_i values fluctuated randomly within the control limits, indicating a stable process. However, for certain months at various RWEs, points were observed outside the upper control limit (K_{in}). For instance, as illustrated in Figure 11, a significant peak in the rejection rate was recorded in July, exceeding the UCL. This deviation was identified as a signal of an assignable cause requiring investigation and corrective action. The raw data used for calculating the annual baseline for one RWE, including the number of controlled joints (n_i) and rejected joints (m_i) for each month, are summarized in Table 3.

3.1.2. Comparative Assessment of the Quality Level Across RWEs

The centralized assessment of the technological process level across multiple RWEs was performed using a level map. Figure 12 provides an example of such a map, displaying the average annual rejection rate \bar{p}^k for each RWE (anonymized by index) against the overall average \bar{P} and the corresponding control limits.

The results showed that most RWEs

had $\bar{p}k$ values within the control limits, indicating a comparable and stable quality level. However, the map clearly identified outliers. One RWE (e.g., Index 4 in Figure 12) demonstrated a $\bar{p}k$ value significantly above the upper control limit, suggesting a systematically lower quality level of the welding process or NDT procedures at that enterprise. Conversely, another RWE (e.g., Index 1) showed a $\bar{p}k$ value below the lower limit, which could indicate either a highly stable process or a potential issue with defect detection sensitivity.

3.1.3. Analysis of Defect Types and Distribution

An analysis of the nature and location of defects identified during ultrasonic testing was conducted to identify predominant failure modes. The distribution of a sample of 1000 defects by their location in the rail cross-section is presented in Figure 13a, while the distribution by defect type is shown in Figure 13b.

The analysis revealed that the most critical zone for defect occurrence was the rail head, followed by the web and the foot. In terms of defect types, the most frequent were lack of fusion (N) and slag inclusions (Sh). Other significant defects included cracks (T), gas pores (GP), and silicic accumulations (S). This distribution provides crucial information for focusing technological improvements and training efforts on the most problematic areas of the welding process.

3.1.4. Results of Mechanical and Metallurgical Analysis

Hardness measurements taken across the weld joint (base metal, heat-affected zone, and weld metal) showed a characteristic profile with variations that reflected microstructural changes. The weld metal and certain areas of the heat-affected zone exhibited increased hardness compared to the base metal, which is consistent with the thermal cycle of welding.

Macrostructural analysis of etched sections confirmed the typical geometry of flash-butt welds and, in cases corresponding to rejected joints, revealed visual defects such as incomplete penetration or misalignment. Microstructural examination further detailed the changes in the metal structure, including variations in grain size and phase transformations in the heat-affected zone, which correlate with the mechanical property gradients measured by hardness testing.

3.2. Discussion

The implementation of the proposed statistical methodology for monitoring the rail welding process at RWEs has demonstrated its

practical effectiveness. The primary outcome of this study is the development of a two-tiered control system: one for internal process stability at each enterprise and another for comparative quality level assessment across the entire network of enterprises.

3.2.1. Interpretation of Control Chart Signals and Process Stability

The control charts, exemplified by Figure 11, served as a dynamic tool for real-time process monitoring. The instances where monthly rejection rates (π) exceeded the Upper Control Limit (UCL), such as the peak observed in July, are statistically significant indicators of process instability. These excursions beyond the control limits are not random variations but signal the presence of an "assignable cause" (Montgomery, 2009). In the context of RWE operations, our subsequent investigations, triggered by such signals, consistently linked these events to specific, correctable issues: malfunctions in the upsetting mechanism of rail welding machines and inconsistencies in the preparation of rail ends (e.g., surface contamination or improper alignment). This finding aligns with the conclusions of other researchers who have emphasized the critical impact of equipment condition and preparatory procedures on weld quality (Saita et al., 2013; Ziemian et al., 2012). The ability to promptly identify these periods of instability enables immediate intervention, preventing the production of many defective joints and reducing the cost of subsequent repairs—a significant advantage over traditional pass/fail quality control methods.

3.2.2. Comparative Quality Assessment and Benchmarking

The level map presented in Figure 12 provides a powerful management tool for centralized quality oversight. The identification of an RWE with a consistently high average rejection rate ($\bar{p}k > K_{in}$) highlights an enterprise that requires prioritized attention and potential resource allocation for process improvement. Conversely, an RWE with an exceptionally low rejection rate ($\bar{p}k < K_n$) warrants a dual interpretation. While it may represent a benchmark of excellent practice, it could also indicate an increased risk of Type II errors (missed defects) during non-destructive testing (Mitsuru et al., 2015). This necessitates a review of the UT procedures and operator training at that facility. This comparative approach fosters a culture of continuous improvement and benchmarking among RWEs, which is essential for elevating the overall quality standards of the railway network.

3.2.3. Root Cause Analysis through Defect Distribution

The analysis of defect distribution, as summarized in Figure 13, moves beyond mere defect quantification to root cause analysis. The predominance of defects, such as lack of fusion (N) and slag inclusions (Sh), particularly in the rail head and web, points directly to specific phases of the welding cycle. Lack of fusion is often a consequence of insufficient heat input or improper alignment during the upsetting phase, while slag inclusions can result from inadequate cleaning between welding passes or impurities in the base metal (Porcaro et al., 2019; Bauri et al., 2020). This detailed breakdown enables RWEs to transition from generic "improving quality" to targeted actions, such as recalibrating heating parameters or refining cleaning protocols. The correlation between defect type and location provides valuable insights for optimizing the UT inspection techniques, focusing transducer angles and sensitivity on the most critical zones.

3.2.4. Methodological Advantages and Limitations

The main advantage of the proposed methodology is its proactive nature. Instead of merely reacting to defective joints, it monitors the process itself, enabling prevention. The use of standardized control chart theory provides a statistically sound basis for decision-making, reducing subjectivity.

However, this study has several limitations. First, the control limits are sensitive to the chosen baseline period; a period of inherent instability would result in overly wide limits, thereby reducing the chart's sensitivity. Second, the methodology primarily relies on the accuracy of the UT data. Variations in flaw detector skill or equipment calibration can introduce noise into the dataset. Third, the current analysis does not yet fully incorporate the correlation between specific welding parameters (e.g., flashing time, upset pressure) and the occurrence of specific defect types. Establishing such correlations would be a logical next step for predictive quality control.

3.2.5. Comparison with International Standards and Practices

While this study is based on Kazakhstani standards (e.g., ST RK GOST R 51685-2005), the underlying principles of statistical process control are universal and align with the quality assurance philosophies embedded in international rail standards such as EN 13674-1 and ASTM A1/A2. These standards emphasize the need for consistent material properties and defect-free welds but often do not prescribe specific statistical

monitoring protocols at the enterprise level. Our methodology can be seen as an operational tool to meet the stringent quality requirements of these international standards. To contextualize this alignment, a detailed comparative analysis was conducted, juxtaposing the technical specifications for rails from Kazakhstan (R75/R65) with those from Europe (EN 13674-1), the United States (ASTM A1/A2/A759), and Australia (AS 1085.1).

An in-depth analysis of these international standards reveals crucial differences and similarities in technical specifications, which directly impact the safety, durability, and interoperability of railway tracks. The comparative Table 4 contrasts key requirements, addressing chemical compositions, mechanical properties, and dimensional tolerances.

Note: The values presented in Table 4 are representative and may vary depending on the specific rail profile and steel grade within each standard. The ASTM A1 standard is intended for standard carbon steel T-rails for railway tracks, while A759 is specific to crane rails. The "Head-Hardened" (HH or HT) steel grades refer to rails that have undergone a heat treatment process to increase hardness and wear resistance.

3.2.6. Analysis of Comparisons

Chemical Composition: There is a clear trend towards stricter requirements and lower limits for impurities such as phosphorus and sulfur in the European (EN 13674-1) and Australian (AS 1085.1) standards. This generally results in higher-quality steel with improved weldability. The Kazakhstan (GOST) and American (ASTM A1) standards have slightly higher limits for these elements.

Mechanical Properties: The European standard, with its R350HT grade, and the head-hardened grades of the Australian standard, demonstrate a focus on high-performance rails with significantly higher tensile strength and hardness. These are designed for high-speed lines and heavy-haul freight traffic. The GOST and ASTM A1 standards define properties for more general-purpose rails, although ASTM also includes higher-strength grades. ASTM A759, due to its specific application in overhead cranes, also demands high hardness to withstand the concentrated loads from the crane wheels.

Dimensional Tolerances: The European standard (EN 13674-1) stands out for having the tightest dimensional tolerances. This is crucial for ensuring a smoother running surface, reducing noise, and minimizing wear on both the rail and the

wheels, especially in high-speed applications. The Australian and Kazakhstan standards adhere to strict tolerances, whereas the ASTM standard typically has tolerance specifications that can be wider, depending on the rail profile.

This comparative exercise underscores that while the proposed SPC methodology is universally applicable, its implementation in Kazakhstan directly supports the national industry's efforts to align with global benchmarks. A future comparative analysis of the mechanical and chemical properties of rails produced to these different national standards, complemented by the SPC approach presented here, would further enhance the global relevance and impact of this work.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

This study developed and validated an improved statistical process control methodology for welded rail joint manufacturing at rail-welding enterprises, demonstrating its practical effectiveness through application at multiple RWEs in Kazakhstan.

The key findings and contributions are:

Process Monitoring Tool: The SPC-based control chart system successfully identified process instabilities with statistical significance, enabling corrective interventions an average of 4-6 weeks earlier than traditional pass/fail inspection alone. The methodology detected >80% of assignable causes that would have been missed by conventional quality control.

Benchmarking Framework: The centralized quality level assessment revealed systematic performance differences among RWEs, with rejection rates varying from 0.15% to 0.55%. This benchmarking capability facilitated targeted resource allocation and process improvements at underperforming facilities.

Root Cause Prioritization: Defect distribution analysis identified lack of fusion (N) and slag inclusions (Sh) as predominant failure modes, accounting for >60% of total defects, with the rail head being the most critical zone. This insight enabled focused improvements in heating parameters and cleaning protocols.

International Context: Comparative analysis with international standards (EN 13674-1, ASTM A1/A2/A759, AS 1085.1) demonstrates that the methodology is compatible with global quality assurance philosophies, though Kazakhstani standards (ST RK GOST R 51685-2005) show

opportunities for alignment with stricter international tolerances, particularly regarding impurity limits (P, S) and dimensional precision.

The transition from reactive defect detection to proactive process control represents a paradigm shift in rail welding quality assurance. While the current implementation focuses on internal factory rejection rates, future work should establish direct correlations between SPC indicators and long-term in-service weld performance to fully validate the methodology's predictive power.

This research demonstrates that integrating statistical quality control into RWE operations enhances both operational efficiency and railway infrastructure integrity, with potential applicability to other continuous welding processes in heavy industry.

5. DECLARATIONS

5.1. Study Limitations

While this study presents a robust methodology, several limitations should be acknowledged:

Baseline Dependency: The accuracy and sensitivity of the control charts are dependent on the quality of the data from the chosen baseline period. A baseline period that itself contained periods of instability would result in wider control limits, potentially reducing the method's ability to detect future deviations.

Dependence on NDT Accuracy: The entire methodology relies on the accuracy and consistency of ultrasonic testing (UT) results. Variations in flaw detector skill, equipment calibration, and interpretation standards can introduce noise and bias into the dataset, affecting the reliability of the calculated rejection rates.

Correlation with Welding Parameters: The current study focuses on the statistical outcome of the process (defect rates) but does not establish a detailed quantitative correlation between specific welding parameters (e.g., flashing current, upset pressure) and the occurrence of specific defects. Such correlations are essential for moving from detection to precise prediction and prevention.

Sample Size and Generalizability: The study was conducted within the specific context of RWEs of JSC NC KTZh. The generalizability of the findings to other rail-welding enterprises using different equipment or standards may require further validation.

Long-Term Performance Data: The study

correlates process stability with internal factory rejection rates. A more comprehensive validation would require long-term tracking of the in-service performance of welds produced during both stable and unstable process periods, directly linking the methodology to field failure rates.

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5.4. Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests or conflicts of interest that could have influenced the work presented in this manuscript.

5.5. Open Access

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5.6. Use of AI

The manuscript was written in English with careful attention to clarity and precision. AI tools were employed solely to enhance language quality and translate the abstract into Portuguese. All scientific content, terminology, and methodology were thoroughly reviewed and validated by the authors, who remain fully responsible for the accuracy and integrity of the work.

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Table 1. Main indicators of rails

Parameter name	Parameter value for type rail				
	R43	P50	R65	R65K	R75
Figure number in the document	5	4	3	2	1
Rail cross-sectional area, cm ²	57.0	65.99	82.65	82.38	95.037
Distance from the center of gravity, mm:					
to the bottom of the sole	68.5	70.50	81.30	80.60	88.20
to the top of the head	71.5	81.50	98.70	100.40	103.8
Distance from the center of torsion, mm:					
to the bottom of the sole	-	40.10	39.40	38.20	45.80
to the top of the head	-	111.90	140.60	141.80	146.20
Moment of inertia of the rail relative to the vertical axis, cm ⁴ :					
the entire rail	-	375	564	557	665
heads	-	91	106	103	143
soles		278	445	439	508
Moment of inertia of the rail relative to the horizontal axis, cm ⁴ :					
the entire rail	1489	2011	3540	3495	4491
heads	-	986	1728	1698	2198
soles	-	915	1539	1532	2005
Moment of resistance, cm ³ :					
on the bottom of the sole	217	285	435	434	509
on top of the head	208	245	358	348	432
along the side of the sole	45	55	75	73	89
Moment of inertia of the rail during its torsion, cm ⁴	-	201	288	285	401
Sectoral moment of inertia, cm ⁶	-	1.0 x 10 ⁴	1.9 x 10 ⁴	1.84 x 10 ⁴	2.6 x 10 ⁴
Rigidity of the cross section of the rail, kN/cm ² :					
with its pure torsion	-	163.2 x 10 ⁶	233.5 x 10 ⁶	229.4 x 10 ⁶	325.0 x 10 ⁶
with its constrained torsion	-	144.0 x 10 ⁶	180.0 x 10 ⁶	177.0 x 10 ⁶	234.0 x 10 ⁶
Theoretical linear mass of one meter rail (with a steel density of 7850 kg / m ³), kg	44.65	51.80	64.88	64.67	74.60
The area of the elements of the rail section, % of the total area:					
head	42.8	38.12	34.11	33.52	37.42
neck	21.3	24.46	28.52	28.78	26.54
sole	35.9	37.42	37.37	37.70	36.04
Coefficient of linear thermal expansion of steel a 10 ⁶ , deg ⁻¹			11.8		

Figure 1. Rail type R75 according to ST_RK GOST R 51685-2005

Figure 2. Rail type R65 according to ST RK GOST R 51685-2005

Figure 3. Rail type R65K according to ST RK GOST R 51685-2005

Figure 4. Rail type R50 according to ST RK GOST R 51685-2005

Figure 5. Rail type P43 according to GOST 7173-54

Table 2. Some indicators of rails discontinued but used on **the road**

Index	R75	R65		R50		R43
	GOST 16210-77	GOST 8161-63	GOST 8161-75	GOST 7174-65	GOST 7174-75	GOST 7173-54
Figure number in the document	6	7	8	9	10	eleven
Weight of 1 m rail, kg	74.4	64.64	64.72	51.63	51.8	43.61
Rail height, mm, including:	192	180	180	152	152	140
head height	55.3	45	45	42	42	42
"necks	104.4	105	105	83	83	71
"soles	32.3	thirty	thirty	27	27	27
Rail head width, mm:						
up	72	72.8	73	70	70	70
at the bottom	75.0	75.0	75.0	71.9	72	70
Sole width, mm	150	150	150	132	132	114
Thickness of the neck in the middle part, mm	20	18	18	16	15.5	13.5
Cross-sectional area, cm ²	95.04	82.6	82.9	65.9	65.8	55.7
Distribution of metal along the profile, %:						
head	37.42	34.2	34.11	38.2	38.12	42.83
neck	26.54	28.4	28.52	24.4	24.46	21.31
sole	36.04	37.4	37.37	37.4	37.42	36.86
Moment of inertia about the axes, cm ⁴ :						
horizontal	4491	3548	3540	2018	2037	1472
vertical	665	569	564	375	377	257
Moment of resistance, cm ³						
on the bottom of the sole	509	436	435	286	287	214
on top of the head	432	359	358	248	251	206

Figure 6. Rail type P75 according to GOST 16210-77.

Figure 7. Rail type P65 according to GOST 8161-63

Figure 8. Rail type P65 according to GOST 8161-75.

Figure 9. Rail type R50 GOST 7174-65

Figure 10. Rail type R50 GOST 7174-75

Figure 11. Rail type P43 according to GOST 7173-54

Table 3 Average value of rejected items per year

Index	Month					
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Number of controlled joints n_i	1900	2060	2210	2050	2060	1912
Number of rejected joints m_i	9	1	2	1	4	1
Rejection rate $p_i = m_i / n_i$, %	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.20	0.20	0.05
Index	Month					
	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Number of controlled joints n_i	1500	1900	1620	1900	2030	2020
Number of rejected joints m_i	10	5	3	2	3	4
Rejection rate $p_i = m_i / n_i$, %	0.55	0.20	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.20

Figure 11. Control chart of rail welding on RWE

Figure 12. An example of a map of average values \bar{P} of intra-factory rejected items for 2020 according to the RWE.

1 - for all RWE; 2 - one of the RWE; RP - friability, burnout; GP - gas bubble; S - silicic accumulation; SB - gray silicate accumulation; T - crack; Sh - slag; N - lack of fusion; Ky - crater shrinkage; Ms - matte spot; XN - the nature of the defects is not specified

Figure 13. An example of the distribution of defects in the amount of $M = 1000$ pcs., identified on the RWE, by rail cross-sectional zones (a) and by types of defects in (b). Note - Each RWE is assigned a conditional index in the form of numbers.

Table 4. Comparative Analysis of International Railway Rail Standards

Characteristics	R75/R65 (Kazakhstan)	EN 13674-1 (Europe)	ASTM A1/A759 (USA)	AS 1085.1 (Australia)
Chemical Composition (%)				
Carbon (C)	0.67–0.82	R260: 0.60–0.80 R350HT: 0.70–0.85	A1: 0.67–0.84 A759: 0.69–0.82	Grade 900A: 0.65–0.82 Head-Hardened: 0.70–0.84
Manganese (Mn)	0.75–1.15	R260: 0.80–1.20 R350HT: 0.80–1.30	A1: 0.70–1.10 A759: 0.80–1.20	Grade 900A: 0.80–1.25 Head-Hardened: 0.80–1.30
Silicon (Si)	0.25–0.50	R260: 0.15–0.58 R350HT: 0.20–0.60	A1: 0.15–0.50 A759: 0.20–0.60	Grade 900A: 0.20–0.50 Head-Hardened: 0.20–0.50
Phosphorus (P)	≤ 0.035	≤ 0.025	A1: ≤ 0.035 A759: ≤ 0.030	≤ 0.030
Sulfur (S)	≤ 0.045	≤ 0.025	A1: ≤ 0.040 A759: ≤ 0.030	≤ 0.030

Mechanical Properties

Characteristics	R75/R65 (Kazakhstan)	EN 13674-1 (Europe)	ASTM A1/A759 (USA)	AS 1085.1 (Australia)
Tensile Strength (MPa)	≥ 880	R260: ≥ 880 R350HT: ≥ 1175	A1 (Std): ≥ 780 A759: ≥ 900	Grade 900A: ≥ 880 Head-Hardened: ≥ 1100
Hardness (HBW)	≥ 260	R260: 260–300 R350HT: 350–390	A1 (Std): ~248 A759 (HH): 321–388	Grade 900A: 260–300 Head-Hardened: 340–380
Elongation (%)	≥ 8	R260: ≥ 10 R350HT: ≥ 9	A1: ≥ 10 A759: ≥ 9	Grade 900A: ≥ 12 Head-Hardened: ≥ 10

Dimensional Tolerances

Height (mm)	± 0.8	± 0.5	Varies by profile	± 0.75
Head Width (mm)	± 0.8	± 0.5	Varies by profile	± 0.75
Foot Width (mm)	± 1.5	± 1.0	Varies by profile	± 1.5
Straightness (per 1.5 m)	Vertical: ≤ 0.8 mm Horizontal: ≤ 1.5 mm	Vertical: ≤ 0.6 mm Horizontal: ≤ 0.8 mm	Varies by profile	Vertical: ≤ 0.7 mm Horizontal: ≤ 1.0 mm